

ENGLISH FOR PRIMARY EDUCATION STUDENTS INNOVATIVE ORGANIZATION OF LESSONS

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Annotation : This in the article initial class in their students foreign language skills increase for pedagogues skill, foreign language in teaching applied different methods and foreign of the language students for How important owner the fact that about word goes. Current in the day each one young generation foreign languages to know time is a requirement.

Key words: foreign language, component, skill, English, time, method, beginning education.

INTRODUCTION

Current in the day in our country young generation knowledgeable and potential bring up for different reforms done is increasing. Of these result like young generation each bilaterally perfect being enough . The last one in years in our country done increased important from reforms one this foreign language development and young generation foreign languages to know is the need . Current in the day each one young foreign languages to know time is a requirement . That's why the school in education foreign languages to teach relatively attention is increasing. Including initial education in the field this direction big attention is being given. And this on the surface different reforms done is increasing.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Primary class in their students foreign language skills increase initial education in the field big importance occupation is enough Because each one knowledge and don't get used to it Beginning initial from education starts and present in the day while foreign languages to know time demand is considered

Foreign languages in teaching teacher pedagogue skill important important has. That is pedagogue employee young to generation foreign languages to know How important owner the fact that about enough absorb take and in students foreign to languages relatively interest wake up take need.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Current in the day of our republic all in the regions school in education foreign languages in teaching important reforms done increased _ Including initial in classes the first from class starting from English , German or French their languages teaching started. We are the former period summary can see we are foreign languages teaching school that his education started from the 5th grade we know can. Next reforms result like while foreign languages teaching began in the 1st grade and initial class students enough book and textbooks with provided. In our country initial in education foreign languages in teaching enough conditions created and foreign language skills increase pedagogue of employees task is considered Foreign language teachers different methods and interesting games using in students foreign to languages relatively interest wake up take and this foreign of the language interesting sides show take and lesson training interesting organize take need.

DISCUSSION

Foreign language lessons in organizing the most interesting and useful of the methods one poems with is work. Below this method sample seeing we go out Speech clear, understandable and understandable to be for poems with work priceless role to play can. They are of speech clarity to reach the most good is a tool. For example , sound exercise to do for the following the poem we get :

Comm aus dem Loch heraus .

Comm my In my Katzenhaus !

Meow , meow , meow .

Pronunciation to teach common strategy (first next , poems with work sequence means) as follows to express can : Students by the poem listen to him understand , teacher phonetic again processing need has been the word separate takes (our in case : Mi-Mausemaus), it students pronunciation does, readers by the sound repeats the word and the word repeats. One whole as consists of.

CONCLUSION

Summary by doing in other words, the beginning class to his students language to teach commitment as not, on the contrary, interesting games and innovative of the methods used without take to go their in the future will receive knowledge for foundation being service to do can. So education system is also its own forward free thoughtful , mature , mature person to educate task by doing puts so , we will be in the future teachers innovative from technologies efficient use ways more perfect work exit with own our contribution let's add can.

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